

Perceived Socio-Political Factors Promoting Sex-For-Grade in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State

Memory Queensoap (PhD)

Department of Foundations, Arts and Social Science Education

Faculty of Education

Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13826354>

Abstract

Sex-for-grade has been seen as a behavioral sexual misconduct invading the academic environment of Nigerian tertiary institutions and becoming hydra-headed of being very difficult to tackle. Its prevalence and causes have been observed to be relative from institution to institution. Therefore, this study was carried out to assess the perceived socio-political factors promoting sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design and was conducted at Federal University Otuoke with a sample of 1000 respondents consisting of lecturers (140) and students (860) which was selected through stratified random sampling technique. The study obtained its data through a validated instrument. Data was analyzed with GraphPad Prism 5 statistical software. Results showed perceived social factors have 4.13 ± 1.14 with 83% level of perception and political factors having 3.92 ± 1.32 with 79% extent of perception. The study observed that there was no significant difference between mean response of students and lecturers on perceived factors enhancing sex-for-grade at $P < .05$. The study concludes that both students and lecturers perceived that there are social and political factors enhancing sex-for-grade in Higher Institutions in Nigeria. Therefore, the researcher recommends that government should formulate action policies and legislate laws that will help tackle sex-for-grade in higher institutions.

Keywords: Social factors, political factors, sex-for-grade, promoting and sexual harassment.

Introduction

The tertiary educational system is established as the third tier of educational level, among others, to develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society through high level relevant manpower training, teaching, research and development, community service, etc. (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2004). According to the educational policy document, the tertiary education is the education given after secondary education in universities, colleges of education, polytechnics, monotechnics including those institutions offering corresponding courses (FRN, 2004). These institutions are expected to bring to reality the educational philosophies and goals of the country. However, among other public concerns, it has been observed that certain immoral activities are rampant and ravaging the educational setting on campus which is majorly known as sexual harassment.

Many scholars had advanced the concept of sexual harassment to behavioral sexual misconduct of a male lecturer towards a female student or a female lecturer towards a male student or vice versa (Ogohi, 2005). In other words, sexual harassment encompasses any sexual misconduct perpetrated either by lecturers or students in view of having academic reward or for self-gratification.

For Udechukwu et al. (2020), sexual harassment has been defined as unsolicited, unwelcome, and unreciprocated sexual overture from a person to elicit unwanted sexual relations from another person. This includes inappropriate sexual overture, subtle and unsubtle persistent behaviour, assault, and actual sexual abuse that may be expressed physically, verbally, or nonverbally, usually from someone with higher power or at a vantage position to less privileged person. In the same vein, sex-for-grade can be described as a situation in which a male lecturer verbally or behaviorally informs a female student that he is ready, willing, and capable of enhancing her marks, scores, and grades from both the continuous assessment and examination, if only she is willing to have sex, kiss, romance, etc., with him before, during and/or after the examination, remarked (Udechukwu, et al., 2020).

Sex-for-grade has become a hydra headed problem that has attracted concern from stakeholders of the educational institutions especially the higher institutions in the country. Among such stakeholders, activists, journalists, and civil liberty organizations including feminism groups had called for urgent attention on the matter. Daikpor (2021) revealed that a large corpus of proof surfaced in October 2019 when a group of Nigerian journalists, led by investigative reporter Kiki Mordi, undertook a covert mission to uncover evidence of sexual harassment by professors in two West African universities- the University of Lagos and the University of Ghana.

Sexual harassment has become a global and extensive practice witnessed in institutions of higher education and has varied and deep effects on persons, groups, and institutions. However, despite all the legal, social, cultural, economic, and political mechanism put in place, there are rampant cases of sexual harassment reported globally, regionally, and nationally (Muthonde, 2022).

It is obvious that sex-for-grade is no longer a local social and academic problem but is a cosmopolitan issue among higher institutions in Nigeria (Smart, 2023). It is a form of sexual assault and harassment becoming visible in all spheres of the academics. Several cases of sexual misconduct have surfaced in the Nigerian institutions and has become a major problem as remarked by Ibrahim et al. (2020). For instance, in Kenya, reports of unfair treatment of students and female workers, sensational reports in the local newspapers of students' intimidation by those in authority, sexual favors for grades, and death of women students from sexual harassment are cited as consequences of sexual harassment (Muthonde, 2022).

The prevalence of sex-for-grade cases are increasingly taking over the academic space of tertiary education in the country. It has been observed that the occurrence of sexual harassment has been under reported. According to (Erinosho, 2024), Sexual harassment (SH) is increasingly reported as an issue of major concern among both students and staff on campuses across the globe and has been confirmed to have social and psychological consequences on the victim. However, the scale of the menace is underplayed because of under-reporting of cases (Ogohi, 2005). This suggests that sexual harassment is rampaging the quality of education expected of in Nigerian institutions. More so, Amalu-Jack (2023) denotes sex-for-grade as sextortion and stated that the troubling reality is that both young female students and married ones are victims of this disturbing pandemic. With sextortion on our campuses, it becomes uncondusive for learning. Nevertheless, there are more unreported cases of sex-for-grades in Nigerian universities than the reported cases. Meanwhile, (Daikpor, 2021) asserted that sexual harassment in Nigerian universities is an

intractable social problem that is just as hard to prove as it is to eliminate. In 2010, a group of Nigerian researchers published the result of a study conducted among female graduates of Nigerian universities which showed that nearly 70% of them had experienced sexual harassment in their institutions of learning, most times at the hands of their male professors or classmates (Daikpor, 2021).

Similarly, Udechukwu et al. (2020), in their study, observed that the common most occurring trend of sex-for-grades is from male lecturer to female students, spurred through nude and indecent dressing and sexual signals at 98.8%. Other trends are from female students to male lecturers which are 62%. Female workers to male lecturers on behalf of their children and relations are 79%. Female lecturers to male students account for 55.6%. This trend analysis indicates that female students seem to be more at risk of sex-grades-in our institutions of higher learning.

This worrisome sex-exploitation or sexual harassment has been seen to be influenced by certain factors. These factors may be relative to institutions however Udechukwu et al. (2020) articulated some causes of sex-for-grade in Nigerian higher institutions which include poor moral upbringing, peer influence, academic laziness, vicarious learning, indecent dressing, emphasis on certificate and social media/ICT. The previous study observed that poor moral upbringing with 55% was rated very high among the causes. Moreover, peer influence is 12%, indecent dressing/nudity represents stand at 20%. Whereas female student's academic laziness and vicarious learning each has 5% over emphasis on certificate has the least rating of 3% (Udechukwu et al., 2020) and (Kenechi, 2024).

In another study, using 73 and 183 university academics and students, identified some causes of sex-for-grade as:

- Lecturer centered which involves lack of self-discipline, moral weakness, poor remuneration of academics, single individual course instructors, unwieldy powers of lecturers over courses.
- Student centered which consists of deliberate use of sex as a weapon by some female students for academic rewards, economic gains, fun, indecent dressing, drug abuse, etc.
- Institutional which relates to lack of clear and transparent procedure for complaints and addressing sexual harassment issues.
- Societal which denotes decline in ethical and moral values in the society (Ibrahim et al., 2020)

From the foregoing, it is obvious to deduce that causes of sex-for-grade are relative and it becomes necessary to investigate further some perceived factors that promote sex-for-grade in Nigerian universities. Empirical investigation of such factors will help in the recommendation of policy actions to tackle sex-for-grade on campuses. Therefore, this study was to examine perceived socio-political factors promoting sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria.

Methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design which enabled the researchers to obtain data at its natural setting without manipulation of any variable. The study selected 1000 participants from the Federal University Otuoke. The sample consisted of 860 students and 140

academic staff drawn through proportionate stratified random sampling from Faculties of Science, Engineering, Education, and Management Sciences. A self-designed instrument titled: Questionnaire on Factors Enhancing sex-for-grade"(QFES) was used to elicit information from respondents. The study instrument (QFES) contained thirteen (13) items with a five-point rating scale in the modified Likert Format. That is, having response level such as Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree with rating 5,4,3,2 and 1 respectively. The researchers validated the instrument of the study through face and content validity methods. The researchers adopted a test-retest method of reliability which on analysis of the data from the double administration with Pearson moment correlation gave a reliability coefficient of 0.78. This value was high enough to consider the study instrument reliable. The instrument was administered by face-to-face method by the aid of four research assistants. Diagrams and simple percentage were used to present the demographic information of respondents while mean and standard deviation were used to analyze data to give answers to the research questions, and t-test was used to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of error probability.

Results

Presentation of Respondents' Demographic Information

Figure 1: A Chart Showing Distribution of Participants by Gender

Figure 1 showed that out of 1000, male has 52% while females consist of 48% implying that more males than female formed the sample of the study.

Figure 2: A Chart Showing Distribution of Participants by Category

A look at figure 2 showing the distribution by category of participants indicates that 14% (140) of lecturers that participated in the study while 86% (860) was all students implying more students took part of the study than lecturers.

Figure 3: A Chart Showing Distribution of Participants by Faculties

Figure 3 indicates that more respondents were made to be involved in the study in the Faculty of Science which contributed 33% (330), education with management science is 22% each while engineering faculty has 21%.

Research Question 1: What are the perceived social factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation

S/N	STATEMENTS	N	X	STD	X%	CM	REMARK
12	mode of dressing of students	1000	4.42	1.16	88		Accepted
13	visiting of lecturers' offices at odd hours	1000	4.62	0.91	92		Accepted
14	peer group influence	1000	3.95	1.27	79		Accepted
15	cultural influence	1000	3.33	1.23	67	3.0	Accepted
16	social media	1000	3.81	1.24	78		Accepted
17	lecturers unguided relationship with students	1000	4.58	1.01	91		Accepted
	GRAND N/X/STD/X%	1000	4.13	1.14	83		Accepted

Source: Research Field work, 2021

Table 1 shows respondents' perception regarding social factors enhancing Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. It was observed in table 1 that mode of dressing of students has 4.42 ± 1.16 mean and standard deviation with 88% very high perception rate, visiting of lecturers' offices at odd hours has 4.62 ± 0.92 mean and standard deviation with 92% very high perception rate, peer group influence has 3.95 ± 1.27 with 79% high perception rate, cultural influence has 3.33 ± 1.23 with 67% high perception, social media has 3.81 ± 1.24 with 78% high perception rate while lecturers unguided relationship with students has 4.53 ± 1.01 with 91% very high perception rate. Meanwhile, the grand mean/standard with mean percentage is 4.13 ± 1.14 with 83% which was greater than the criterion mean (3.0), indicating that respondents very highly perceived that the investigated social factors enhance Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions.

Research Question 2: What are the perceived political factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria?

Table 2
Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation

S/N	STATEMENTS	N	X	STD	X%	CM	REMARK
18	poor enforcement of sexual harassment rules and regulation by university authority	1000	4.25	1.34	85		Accepted
19	no legal framework to punish offenders	1000	3.8	1.54	76	3.0	Accepted
20	government apathy to sexual harassment cases	1000	3.53	1.34	71		Accepted
21	university management apathy to sexual cases	1000	4.45	1.02	89		Accepted
22	lack of political will	1000	3.86	1.24	77		Accepted
23	negligence from trade unions	1000	3.1	1.65	62		Accepted
24	apathy from students' union	1000	4.48	1.13	90		Accepted
	Grand N/X/STD/X%	1000	3.92	1.32	79		Accepted

Source: Research Field work, 2021

Table 2 shows respondents' perception regarding political factors enhancing Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. It was observed in table 2 that poor enforcement of sexual harassment rules and regulation by university authority has 4.25 ± 1.34 mean and standard deviation

with 85% very high perception rate, no legal framework to punish offenders has 3.80 ± 1.54 mean and standard deviation with 76% high perception rate, government apathy to sexual harassment cases has 3.53 ± 1.34 with 71% high perception rate, university management apathy to sexual cases has 4.45 ± 1.02 with 89% very high perception, lack of political will has 3.86 ± 1.24 with 77% high perception rate, negligence from trade unions has 3.1 ± 1.65 with 62% high perception rate while apathy from students' union has 4.48 ± 1.13 with 90% very high perception rate. Meanwhile, the grand mean/standard with mean percentage is 3.92 ± 1.32 with 79% which was greater than the criterion mean (3.0), indicating that respondents highly perceived that the investigated political factors enhance Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions.

Null hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived social factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria

Table 3
Summary of t-test Statistics

Comparing Pairs	N	X	STD	t-ratio	Df	P val.	Decision
Students	860	24.87	3.85				
Vs				0.9895	998	0.0132	Ho accepted
Lecturers	140	24.86	4.40				(ns) at 0.05

Source: Research Field Work

It can be discerned from table 3 that for the number of students (N) is 86 and the students' group has mean (X) and standard deviation (STD) of 24.87 ± 3.85 . For lecturers, Number participated (N) is 14, mean with standard deviation are 24.86 ± 4.40 . While the t-ratio is 0.9895, degree of freedom (df) is 998, P value is 0.0132 at P value of 0.05, that is, $P > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived social factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions is accepted. This means that both lecturers and students perceived in the same way that the social factors under investigation enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived political factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria

Table 4
Summary of t-test Statistics

Comparing Pairs	N	X	STD	t-ratio	Df	P val.	Decision
Students	860	27.38	4.59				
Vs				1.841	998	0.0687	Ho accepted
Lecturers	140	24.79	6.55				(ns) at 0.05

Source: Research Field Work

It can be discerned from table 4 that for the number of students (N) is 860 and the students' group has mean (X) and standard deviation (STD) of 27.38 ± 4.59 . For lecturers, Number participated (N) is 140, mean with standard deviation are 24.79 ± 6.55 . While the t-ratio is 1.84, degree of freedom (df) is 998, *P* value is 0.0687 at *P* value of 0.05, that is, $P > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived political factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions is accepted. This means that both lecturers and students perceived in the same way that the political factors under investigation enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions.

Discussion

This study was purposed to assess perceived socio-political factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institution in Nigeria. The study selected 1000 participants from the students' folk (86%) and lecturers (14%). One of the findings of this study was that social factors can enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions. These perceived social factors identified by this study include that mode of dressing of students, visiting of lecturers' offices at odd hours, peer group influence, cultural influence, social media, and lecturers' unguided relationship with students. Meanwhile, the grand mean/standard deviation with mean percentage is 4.13 ± 1.14 with 83% which was greater than the criterion mean (3.0), indicating that respondents highly perceived that the investigated social factors enhance Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions. The study observed that both lecturers and students perceived them in the same way. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived social factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions is accepted. Ogah (2004) reported that indecent dressing on campus has been an outcry in many universities. Social factors seem promote sex-for-grade in higher institution.

The study observed that respondents highly perceived that political factors can promote sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. The political factors perceived very highly are poor enforcement of sexual harassment rules and regulation by university authority, no legal framework to punish offenders, government apathy to sexual harassment cases, university management apathy to sexual cases, lack of political will, negligence from trade unions and apathy from students' union. Meanwhile, the grand mean/standard with mean percentage is 3.92 ± 1.32 with 79% which was greater than the criterion mean (3.0), indicating that respondents highly perceived that the investigated political factors enhance Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions. Lecturers and students in a similar response perceived these factors as political factors promoting sex-for-grade in higher institutions. This was supported in the work that reveal that the sampled higher educational institutions in Nigeria employed mostly bolstering, diminish and denial crisis response strategies in their press releases in reaction to the BBC's sex-for-grades report to protect their own unique institutional reputations (Fadipe & Bakenne, 2020). It is clear indication of negligence from university authorities taking no responsibility of sexual harassment cases.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers conclude that socio-political factors can enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. Some of these perceived socio-political factors

were indecent dressing, visitation of lecturers by students, especially females at odd hours, lecturers' unguided relationships with students, lack of political will, university management apathy to reported sexual harassment cases, apathy from students' union, etc. The study concludes that both students and lecturers affirm similarly the observed socio-political factors as influencers of sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria.

Recommendations

- Government should enforce legislations regarding sexual harassment and show strong political will against sexual crimes on campuses in higher institutions in Nigeria.
- University management should form a synergy among universities to tackle cases of sexual harassment and should not adopt denial response strategy for sexual harassment cases.
- Non-Governmental Organization should take the campaign against sex-for-grade on campuses by carrying out symposiums, seminars, conferences, and advocacy.

Reference

- Amalu-Jack, G. (2023, October 31). *Sex-for-Grades as pandemic on campuses*. Retrieved from Nigerian Tribune: <https://tribuneonline.ng/nsitf-kickstart-action>
- Daikpor, I. (2021, May 15). *Sex for grade: Sexual harassment in Nigerian Universities and documentary activism*. Retrieved from Medium.html.: <https://www.immadaikp.medium.com>
- Erinosho, S. (2024). *Sexual harassment on campus: A study in Nigeria university*. Retrieved from Academia Premium: <https://independent.academia.edu/Erinosho?swp=tc=au-99927865>
- Fadipe, I. A., & Bakenne, N. A. (2020). BBC sex-for-grades-report: Nigeria tertiary institutions' crisis management strategies and stakeholders' reactions. *The Jjournal of Society and Media*, 4(1), doi:10.26740/jsm.v4n1.p156-179., 156-179.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN). (2004). *National policy on education, 4th ed.* Federal Ministry of Education.
- Ibrahim, M. A., Sogbanmu, T. O., & Omoju, O. (2020, June). *Sex for grade in Nigerian tertiary institutions: Evidence-Based recommendations for policy action*. Retrieved from Nigerian Young Academic, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.133352.24321: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358749149>
- Kenechi, S. (2024, May 3). *Senate counters FG, says minimum age requirement for varsity admission not yet a law*. Retrieved from The Cable: <https://www.thecable.ng>senate..>
- Muthonde, C. K. (2022, May 17). *Sexual harassment and related policy in higher institution of learning in Kenya*. Retrieved from SPRINGER LINK: <https://www.link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-95622-6>
- Ogah, F. (2004). An address presented at the 2004 convocation ceremony by the Vice Chancellor of Ebonyi State University. Abakiliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria: Ebonyi State University.
- Ogohi, U. (2005). *Sexual abuse management for University sub sector*. Federal Government Printer.
- Ogugua, A. (2024, February 15). *Sexual harassment trial: ICPC closes case against UNICAL don*. Retrieved from PRNigeria News: <https://www.prnigeria.com>
- Smart, E. A. (2023). The effect of sex-for-grade practice in higher educational institutions in Edo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Sciences (IJLRHSS)*, 6(10), 177-184.

Udechukwu, J. A., Nwankwo, K. O., & Okeke, K. C. (2020). Causes, types and consequences of sex-for-grades in institution of higher learning in Anambra State: Implications for guidance and counselling. *AL-HIKMAH Journal of Education*, 7(1) , 56-61.